

RESEARCH ON CLASSIFICATION OF POTATO DISEASE LEAVES BASED ON XCEPTION

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Abstract: Aiming at the difficulty in identifying potato early blight and late blight, this paper conducts a disease classification study based on Xception. Due to the similar initial symptoms of the two diseases, the traditional expert identification method has many limitations, while accurate identification is crucial for disease prevention and control. The research takes relevant leaves as the object, adopts the "Potato Disease Leaf Dataset v1", which is divided into training set, validation set and test set. The model is optimized through four groups of comparative experiments: the test set accuracy of the basic convolutional neural network model is 77.9% with overfitting; after introducing data augmentation, the accuracy is improved to 82.2%, and the overfitting is alleviated but there is still a gap; the transfer learning based on Xception makes the accuracy exceed 91%, and the overfitting is basically eliminated; after model fine-tuning, the accuracy exceeds 95% with excellent generalization ability. The results show that this optimization path provides a reusable framework for intelligent diagnosis of agricultural diseases, especially suitable for the identification of segmenting crop diseases with scarce samples.

Keywords: Potato, Disease leaves, Convolutional Neural Network, Xception, Dataset

1 Research Background and Significance

In recent years, with the continuous expansion of potato planting scale, the incidence range and damage degree of early blight and late blight have also increased. In the early stage of these two diseases, they mostly present as leaf spots, and their symptoms are highly similar, which are very easy to be confused. Once a misjudgment is made, it often delays the best time for prevention and treatment. The traditional way of disease identification mainly relies on expert visual diagnosis, which not only requires the identifiers to have rich professional knowledge, but also is easily affected by subjective experience. At the same time, it has the problems of being time-consuming and difficult to achieve efficient diagnosis of diseases.

Accurate identification and localization of disease spots are key links in potato disease prevention

and control [1-2]. Therefore, developing an efficient and accurate intelligent identification method for potato diseases has important practical application value [3]. In view of this, this paper takes potato early blight, late blight and healthy leaves as the research objects, aiming to construct a disease identification model based on the deep convolutional neural network Xception. Through the analysis of potato leaf images, it realizes the automatic identification of healthy state, early blight and late blight, so as to provide technical support for the timely prevention and control of diseases.

healthy

early blight

late blight

Figure 1: Comparison between healthy potato leaves and diseased potato leaves

2 Potato Disease Leaf Classification Model Based on Xception

To further enhance the accuracy and generalization ability of potato disease recognition, this study introduces the Xception deep learning model and systematically conducts classification experiments on potato early blight, late blight, and healthy leaves through strategies such as dataset optimization, transfer learning, and model fine-tuning.

2.1 Introduction to Xception

The Xception network is an improved model of InceptionV3 proposed by Chollet F [4] after Google's Inception series. Its core improvement lies in adopting depthwise separable convolution to replace the feature response operation of multi-scale convolution kernels in Inception V3. Figure 2 shows the basic structure of Xception: first, 1×1 convolution kernels are used for cross-channel convolution, and then 3×3 convolutions are applied to each output channel individually, with the number of 3×3 convolutions being consistent with the number of output channels of the 1×1 convolutions. The network architecture contains 36 convolutional layers, which together form the basic network for feature extraction. In the subsequent processing of the convolutional layers, each layer is equipped with a logistic regression layer, and a fully connected layer may be randomly added before the logistic regression layer. In addition, the 36 convolutional layers are orderly divided into 14 modules, among which the Entry flow contains 4, the Middle flow contains 8, and the Exit flow contains 2. Except for the first and last modules, each of the remaining modules is designed

with residual structure connections to further improve network performance.

Figure 2: Xception Basic Structure

2.2 Dataset Splitting and Optimization

To ensure the scientificity of model training and the objectivity of evaluation, this study conducts refined splitting on the "Potato Disease Leaf Dataset v1 [5]", dividing it into three independent subsets: training set, validation set, and test set. Each subset is structured with a three-level folder hierarchy according to categories, storing images of early blight leaves, late blight leaves, and healthy leaves respectively. Moreover, the distribution ratio of the three types of images in each subset remains consistent to avoid the interference of category imbalance on model training. The specific statistical information of the split dataset is shown in Table 1:

Table 1: Statistical Information Table of the Split Dataset

Categories	Training dataset (pieces)	Validation dataset (pieces)	Test dataset (pieces)	Total
Early blight leaves	1989	994	994	3977
Late blight leaves	1245	622	622	2489
Healthy leaves	767	383	383	1533
Subtotal	4001	1999	1999	7999

As can be seen from the table, the sample size ratio of the training set, validation set, and test set is 2:1:1. This not only ensures the scale of the training set

to support the learning of model parameters, but also realizes the tuning of model hyperparameters and the evaluation of generalization ability through the independent validation set and test set respectively, laying a data foundation for the reliability of subsequent experiments.

2.3 Model Training and Performance Optimization Experiments

To systematically verify the effectiveness of different deep learning strategies in potato disease recognition, this study designed four sets of progressive comparative experiments. Starting from the construction of basic models to advanced transfer learning and fine-tuning, the model performance is gradually optimized. The specific processes and results are as follows:

2.3.1 Training of basic convolutional neural network model: Establishing a performance baseline

To clarify the basic capabilities of traditional deep learning architectures in potato disease recognition tasks, a simple convolutional neural network with two convolutional layers was first constructed as a benchmark model. Its structural details are as follows:

Input layer: Receives RGB images with a size of 150×150 ($IMAGE_SIZE=150 \times 150$);

Feature extraction layer:

1st convolutional layer: Uses 3×3 convolution kernels, 16 neurons, combined with ReLU activation function, followed by a 2×2 max-pooling layer;

2nd convolutional layer: Uses 3×3 convolution kernels, 32 neurons, combined with ReLU activation function, followed by a 2×2 max-pooling layer;

Classification layer: After flattening the features through the Flatten layer, it is connected to a fully connected layer activated by ReLU, and finally outputs the classification probabilities of 3 categories (early blight, late blight, healthy) through the Softmax function.

Figure 3: Structure of the basic convolutional neural network

After 100 iterations (epochs=100) on the training set, the recognition accuracy of this model on the test set reaches 77.9%. It can be seen from the training curve (left graph of Figure 4) that the model exhibits significant overfitting characteristics: the training set accuracy (blue dots) increases to more than 95% with the number of iterations, while the validation set accuracy (polyline) tends to be flat in the later stage, stabilizing at around 75%. This phenomenon indicates that although the basic model can fit the training data well, due to the limited network depth and insufficient feature extraction capability, its generalization ability to unseen test data is weak.

Figure 4: Training curves of the basic convolutional neural network

2.3.2 Introducing Data Augmentation Technology: Alleviating Overfitting Issues

To address the overfitting problem of the aforementioned basic model, data augmentation strategies are introduced, including operations such as random translation, scaling, rotation, brightness adjustment, and histogram equalization. The generalization ability of the model is improved by expanding the diversity of training samples. With the same network structure and training parameters (100 epochs), the accuracy of the test set is increased to 82.2%. It can be seen from the optimized training curve (left graph of Figure 5) that the validation set accuracy (polyline) is increased by about 7 percentage points compared with the basic model, and the gap with the training set accuracy (dots) is reduced from 20% to 8%. This indicates that data augmentation effectively alleviates overfitting by expanding the sample distribution space. However, the gap between the validation set accuracy and the training set accuracy remains above 8%, indicating that data augmentation alone is insufficient to completely eliminate the model's over-reliance on training data, and further optimization of the network architecture is required.

Figure 5: Training curves of the basic convolutional neural network after data augmentation

2.3.3 Transfer Learning Based on Xception: Enhancing Feature Extraction Capability

In view of the performance bottleneck of the basic model, the Xception model pre-trained on the ImageNet dataset is introduced for transfer learning. This model adopts a depthwise separable convolution structure and has stronger feature abstraction capability, which is particularly suitable for image classification tasks. The experimental strategies are as follows:

Feature extractor: The convolutional base of Xception is retained, and its pre-trained parameters are frozen. The general image features (such as edges,

textures, and shapes) learned by it are used to extract the underlying features of potato leaves;

Classifier reconstruction: Replace the top classifier of the original model and design a custom densely connected layer, which includes 1 fully connected layer (128 convolutional channels) with ReLU activation function, and finally outputs the probabilities of 3 categories through Softmax ;

Training strategy: The parameters of the convolutional base are fixed, and only the newly constructed classifier is trained for 100 epochs.

The results show that the accuracy of the test set is quickly improved to over 91%. The training curve (left graph of Figure 6) shows that both the validation set accuracy and the training set accuracy reach about 95%, and their trends are highly consistent, with the overfitting phenomenon basically eliminated. This indicates that transfer learning, by reusing the general features learned from large-scale data, significantly reduces the model's dependence on small-sample datasets, while improving the classification accuracy and generalization ability.

Figure 6: Training curves of transfer learning based on Xception

2.3.4 Model Fine-Tuning: Adapting to Specific Disease Features

To further explore the model's ability to recognize specific features of potato diseases (such as the ringed lesions of early blight and the water-soaked edges of late blight), fine-tuning was performed on the basis of transfer learning:

Unfreezing strategy: Unfreeze the 14th layers of the Xception convolutional base, while retaining the parameters of the bottom 13 layers to maintain the ability of general feature extraction;

Learning rate adjustment: A smaller learning rate (1/10 of the initial learning rate) is adopted to avoid violent parameter updates from damaging the learned general features;

Training strategy: Jointly train the unfrozen convolutional layers and the classifier for 100 epochs, enabling the model to learn disease-specific features in a targeted manner while retaining general features.

The final test set accuracy exceeded 95%. The training curve (left graph of Figure 7) shows that both the validation set and training set accuracies were stably above 95%, indicating that the model still has excellent generalization ability at high precision. It can effectively distinguish potato early blight, late blight and healthy leaves, fully meeting the actual needs of rapid field diagnosis.

Figure 7: Training curves of the Xception-based transfer learning model after fine-tuning

3 Experimental Conclusions

Through the gradual optimization of four sets of experiments, the accuracy of potato disease leaf classification has increased from 77.9% of the basic model to over 95% after fine-tuning, which verifies the significant advantages of deep learning technology in plant disease recognition. Data augmentation effectively alleviates overfitting by expanding sample diversity, but its improvement in accuracy is limited. Transfer learning, by means of reusing general features, breaks through the limitation of small samples and is the key to the leap in accuracy. Fine-tuning further taps the model's potential by adapting to specific features, achieving the peak performance. This optimization path provides a reusable technical

framework for intelligent diagnosis of agricultural diseases, and is especially suitable for the recognition scenarios of segmenting crop diseases with scarce samples.

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